

TREATMENT OF CORONARY HEART DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS AND CRITICAL LOWER LIMB ISCHEMIA

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Annotation: CAG before the intervention on the lower limb is indicated in about 30% of patients with DM and KINK, belonging to the group of patients with high cardiovascular risk. High risk in such patients was defined as a recent MI, angina pectoris of a high functional class, signs of severe BIM, life-threatening cardiac arrhythmias or signs of significant myocardial ischemia obtained as a result of tests to detect stress-induced myocardial ischemia

Keywords. diabetes, metabolism, cardiovascular, critical lower limb ischemia, coronary, electrocardiogram.

Despite the successes achieved in the treatment and prevention of diabetes mellitus (DM), clear guidelines in the principles of its treatment and criteria for compensation of carbohydrate metabolism (ACCORD (Action to Control Cardiovascular Risk in Diabetes), ADVANCE (Action in Diabetes and Vascular Disease –Preterax and Diamicron Modified Control Evaluation) studies, the incidence of complications of diabetes remains high [2,4,6,8,10,12]. The leading position among them is occupied by macroangiopathy, primarily lesions of large arteries and arteries of the lower extremities. Ischemic heart disease (CHD), developing in patients with DM, critical lower limb ischemia (KINK), significantly reduce life expectancy and increase the risk of death, mainly from CHD. Despite the available literature data on a poor prognosis in patients with DM and KINK, the severity of coronary artery disease and the features of coronary artery disease (CA) in this group of patients have not been studied enough. Currently existing recommendations for the diagnosis and treatment of DM [Société Française d'endocrinologie (SFD) & Société Française d'cardiologie (SFC), 2012], peripheral artery diseases (POA) and KINK [American College of Cardiology (ACC)/ American Heart Society (AHA), 2006; American Society of Cardiology (ESC), 2011], as well as recommendations for the treatment of various forms of coronary heart disease [ESC 2006, ESC 2010; ESC 2011;] cannot be fully applied in this category of patients [13,15,17,19,21,23].

First of all, the peculiarity of such patients is the need for a multidisciplinary approach to medical care, the difficulty of identifying the leading pathology, determining the priority of specialized treatment. The number of complications

of diabetes is inevitably growing, primarily macrovascular. These complications are the main cause of disability and mortality of patients with DM. There are very few studies in which the features of the course of coronary heart disease in such a severe category of patients as patients with DM and KINK were studied and evaluated [14,16,18,20,22,25].

First of all, the peculiarity of such patients is the need for a multidisciplinary approach to medical care, the difficulty of identifying the leading pathology, determining the priority of specialized treatment. The number of complications of diabetes is inevitably growing, primarily macrovascular. These complications are the main cause of disability and mortality of patients with DM. There are very few studies in which the features of the course of coronary heart disease in such a severe category of patients as patients with DM and KINK were studied and evaluated [1,3,5,7,9,11,24].

However, at present, the tactics of diagnosis and treatment of coronary heart disease in patients with DM and KINK have not been adequately developed. It is required to study the occurrence of "acute" and "severe" forms of coronary heart disease, to determine the need and timing of intervention on CA in patients with DM and KINK, to develop clear algorithms for the management of such patients with combined pathology.

The purpose of the study. To study the frequency of occurrence of various forms of coronary heart disease in patients with DM and KINK, to develop an algorithm for the diagnosis and treatment of coronary heart disease in patients of this group, depending on the clinical picture.

Materials and methods: In the "Endocrinological Research Center" of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan, in the period from November 2019 to December 2022, a single-stage open cohort study was conducted, which included 118 patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes hospitalized due to the development of KINK. Women predominated among the patients.

The diagnosis of DM was established according to WHO criteria [WHO/IDF, 2016]; KINK was determined according to the diagnostic criteria of the second Transatlantic Agreement on Peripheral Artery Diseases (POA) [2017]: the presence of pain in the limb in the patient at rest, and/or ulcers or gangrene caused by proven pathology of the arteries of the limb. The diagnosis of acute coronary syndrome (ACS), angina pectoris, pain-free myocardial ischemia, chronic heart failure (CHF), arterial hypertension was made according to the recommendations of the All-Russian Scientific Society of Cardiology [2016]. The Wagner classification was used to assess injuries on the limb [Lavery LA, 2016].

All patients underwent general clinical studies, including: clinical blood analysis; biochemical blood analysis, with determination of levels of total protein, albumin, creatinine, urea nitrogen, glucose, uric acid, potassium, sodium, bilirubin, hepatic transaminases, total cholesterol of high and low density lipoproteins, triglycerides, as well as a coagulogram with determination of fibrinogen levels. The level of glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) and the level of glycemia during the day (glycemic profile) were determined.

In all 118 patients, an electrocardiogram (ECG) was recorded within the first hours after admission: rhythm, heart rate, presence of ventricular rhythm disturbances, negative T waves and pathological Q waves, as well as ST segment dynamics: elevation or depression were assessed. The Sardiofax M ECG-1350 device (Nihon Kohden, Japan) was used for ECG registration.

As a result of the examination of 118 patients with DM and KINK, it was found that more than half of the patients (58.5%) suffered from various forms of coronary heart disease. Angina pectoris of functional class II (FC) was the most common.

As a result of the study, it was found that the majority of patients suffered from hypertension (GB). However, at admission, only 18% of patients had blood pressure optimally controlled. Almost half of the patients showed signs of CHF, in most cases corresponding to II FC. Only 17 (14%) patients were diagnosed with CHF before hospitalization, while the remaining 39 (86%) were diagnosed with CHF for the first time.

When registering an ECG, 12 patients at rest showed signs of myocardial ischemia, while 5 patients did not have a typical angina clinic or its equivalents. In the remaining 106 patients, no signs of myocardial ischemia were detected on the resting ECG.

Unstable ventricular tachycardia was registered in 5 patients (4.23%) with CMECG (4 patients (3.4%) had no angina attacks or their equivalents), 4 (3.4%) patients had atrial fibrillation/flutter paroxysm, 4 patients (3.4%) had transient grade IIIII CA blockade, in 3 patients (2.54%) - AV blockade of the II degree, type 2. Significant ST segment depression was recorded in 2 patients (1.7%) with Holter ECG monitoring (HMECG), however, only 1 of them noted the appearance of discomfort behind the sternum in the study diary. The results of the analysis of ECG data in patients with DM and KINK showed that ventricular arrhythmias (ventricular extrasystole and ventricular tachycardia runs) ($p=0.048$), as well as atrial fibrillation/flutter ($p=0.003$) and atrioventricular blockades ($p=0.021$)

were significantly more common in patients with coronary artery disease compared with patients without IBS.

During resting echocardiography, 8 patients were diagnosed with aortic stenosis for the first time, and 12 patients were found to have violations of the local kinetics of the left ventricle (LV) for the first time. No significant lesions of the pericardium, stenoses of the 12 left atrioventricular orifice and aneurysms of the ascending aorta were detected.

As a result of our analysis, it was found that with increasing age, both in men ($p=0.037$) and in women ($p=0.001$) and regardless of gender ($p<0.050$), the incidence of coronary heart disease increased.

Women were slightly more likely than men to suffer from coronary heart disease, but this difference was statistically unreliable ($p>0.050$).

We have not revealed a significant effect on the development of CHD of the duration of DM, the level of HbA1c, the presence of dyslipidemia. Patients with coronary heart disease were somewhat more often on insulin therapy than on therapy with oral hypoglycemic drugs (PSP); more often they had CKD 3 and more severe damage to the soft tissues of the limb. However, these differences turned out to be statistically unreliable. Patients with coronary heart disease were significantly more likely to have a reduced ejection fraction (EF) and a lower GFR. No patients with CKD 0 were identified in the study.

When analyzing the clinical data of patients with DM and KINK with BIM and stress angina (HF) I-III FC, it was revealed that patients with BIM were younger, more often suffered myocardial infarction, and more often had more severe limb tissue damage.

Postinfarction atherosclerosis (PICS) was in 9 (75%) patients with BIM, coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) was performed by 3 (5.2%), and percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) – 0, previous limb revascularization (RC) – 3 (25%) patients. There were no patients with CKD 0 in the study. In patients with HF, the duration of DM was longer, and the level of HbA1 was higher than in those without HF. However, these differences turned out to be statistically unreliable. Patients with BIM, compared with patients with clinical angina, had a significantly less severe stage of CKD.

In the clinical evaluation of the ulcerative limb lesion according to Wagner, the largest number of patients 44 (37.29%) had a deep ulcerative defect, which corresponded to the second degree of lesion. A slightly smaller number of patients (41 (34.75%)) had a deeper lesion (with the formation of an abscess and/or osteomyelitis) – Wagner III. Only 5 (4.2%) patients did not have a

wound on an ischemic limb. The most common localization of the ulcerative process is the toes of the foot 43 (37%), the heel area is less common - 34 (29%), 40 (34%) patients had a combination of finger and heel area lesions.

The most common lesion is a combination of a lesion of the femoral–popliteal segment and the tibial-stop segment, whereas an isolated lesion of the femoral–popliteal segment was not typical for this category of patients (Table 8). There was no significant difference in the localization of arterial disease of the lower extremities in patients with coronary artery disease, compared with patients without coronary artery disease ($p= 0.72$), as well as patients with BIM and angina pectoris ($p=0.56$).

Special attention was paid to hypoglycemic therapy. In general, 115 patients (98%) underwent correction of sugar-reducing therapy: due to decompensation of carbohydrate metabolism, 28 patients were prescribed insulin therapy for the first time, 11 patients needed a reduction in the dose of insulin, 52 patients had an increased dose of insulin, 24 patients intensified PSP therapy. In all patients (18 patients) who had previously received Metformin therapy, the drug was canceled due to the presence of a high risk of lactic acidosis against the background of KINK, as well as in connection with the upcoming radiopaque examination and surgical intervention. Iron preparations were prescribed to 21 patients due to the presence of anemia (7 patients - normocytic, 14 - microcytic), in patients with severe renal insufficiency (5 patients) - erythropoietin preparations. All patients in the preoperative period were treated for contrast-induced nephropathy: infusion of a saline solution of 1000-2000 ml was used after the intervention. In 12 patients with glomerular filtration rate (GFR) < 45 ml/min/1.73m², ACE/ARBs were canceled at least 48 hours before X-ray contrast intervention. In 5 patients with GFR < 30 ml/min/1.73m², an ultrahemofiltration session was performed after the intervention.

A significant relationship was revealed between the presence of diabetic retinopathy (DR), left ventricular LV and the duration of DM disease - patients with DR had a lower left ventricular LV ($p=0.041$). These patients also had a long duration of DM ($p=0.002$). There were no significant differences in the severity of CKD in patients depending on the presence or absence of coronary heart disease. There was no relationship between coronary heart disease, duration of diabetes, gender and age.

Conclusions: 1. In the examined group of patients with diabetes mellitus and critical ischemia of the lower extremities, coronary heart disease was detected

in 60% of cases. 16% of them were diagnosed with angina pectoris of a high functional class, and 8% had acute coronary syndrome.

2. Pronounced "pain-free" myocardial ischemia occurred in 10% of patients with DM and KINK.

3. In patients with DM and KINK, the clinical picture of coronary heart disease is often atypical, in this regard, the severity of coronary heart disease is difficult to assess based on the patient's complaints. When determining the tactics of treatment, it is important to establish not the presence, but the severity of coronary heart disease.

4. Patients with DM and KINK should determine the degree of operational risk before performing surgery on the limb and, if necessary, conduct an examination (stress echocardiography, coronary angiography) aimed at clarifying the severity of coronary artery disease.

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